

YOU'VE TESTED POSITIVE FOR COVID-19. NOW WHAT?

Whether you have symptoms or not, if you test positive for COVID-19, follow these steps to care for yourself and help protect others.

Stay home, isolated from other people

- Even if you don't have symptoms, do not leave your home for 10 days, except to get medical care.
- Get rest and stay hydrated.
- Stay alone in a closed room away from other people and pets, as much as possible.
- Use a different bathroom, if possible.

Monitor (or watch for) your symptoms

- Stay in touch with your doctor or local health department. Follow their instructions.
- Seek medical care if you have trouble breathing or any emergency warning signs.
- If you have an emergency, call 911 and let the operator know you need care for someone who has or may have COVID-19. You can also call ahead to your local emergency room.
- Try to avoid public transportation, ride-sharing, or taxis .

Clean your hands often

- Wash your hands often with soap and water for at least 20 seconds, especially after blowing your nose, coughing, sneezing, going to the bathroom, and before eating or preparing food.
- Use hand sanitizer when soap and water are not available.
- Avoid touching your eyes, nose, and mouth.

Wear a mask and cover coughs and

- If you have to be around other people or pets, wear a mask, even at home. Make sure your mask covers your nose and mouth.
- Try to stay at least six feet away from other people.
- Children under age two, anyone who has trouble breathing, or anyone who is not able to remove the mask without help should not use a mask.

WARNING SIGNS INCLUDE BUT ARE NOT LIMITED TO:

- Trouble breathing
- Constant pain or pressure in the chest
- New confusion
- Not able to wake-up or stay awake.
- Pale, gray, or blue-colored skin, lips, or nail beds, depending on skin tone

Help slow the spread

- Even without symptoms you can still spread COVID-19 to others. Let anyone with whom you were in close contact in the past 48 hours (2 days) know you tested positive so they can isolate and get tested.
- If someone from the health department calls you, you should answer the phone. Knowing your test results or if you have been around someone else who tested positive will help slow the spread.